

Reducing Traffic Congestion Using AI Car-detector system, Smart Traffic Lights and Automated Communication

Almeqdad Mohamed zeina¹, Mostafa Saleh Abd Elghany²

¹Kafr El-Sheikh STEM high School, Kafr El-Sheikh, Egypt

²Kafr El-Sheikh STEM high School, Kafr El-Sheikh, Egypt

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Overview:

With the high rate of natural increase and traffic congestion, the world requires innovation solutions. This research demonstrates that traffic congestion can be reduced by using an AI Car-detector system, Smart-Controlled traffic lights, sending suggestions of alternative roads, and communication between emergency vehicles and drivers.

Summary:

This project addresses Egypt's Grand Challenge of reducing urban traffic congestion and its bad consequences; such as increased travel time, fuel consumption, and air pollution. This occurs through integrating Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI). The aim of this study is to design a smart, real-time traffic management system which senses road conditions, analyses congestion levels, and controls traffic lights to improve traffic flow and enhance emergency-lane accessibility.

The prototype includes hardware and software components. A USB webcam, Arduino-controlled traffic light module, and a Python-based AI detection model using YOLO and DeepSORT tracking. The system continuously analyses live video to count vehicles and detect congestion, that if five or more Vehicles are identified, the system will automatically modify the traffic-light cycle by increasing the green-light duration and decreasing the red-light period. Instantly, it provides real-time changes to a web-based dashboard. It also sends notifications through a Telegram bot that guides other less-congested routes. Moreover, the system features an emergency-lane clearance, where paramedics can trigger an "Emergency" command that alerts nearby drivers.

Testing showed that the prototype successfully detected cars by 90% accuracy, identified congestion, responded to sudden changes with high accuracy, and reduced the waiting time from 30s to 24s through 70s (20% reduction). It also accomplished reliable communication between sensing and alerting with low suspend.

The major conclusion is that combining AI detection with ICT-based communication significantly improves efficiency and supports faster emergency-vehicle clearance.

Introduction:

Egypt suffers from challenges that are mainly addressed as 11 Egypt's grand challenges. This project works on reducing traffic congestion and pollution, specifically air pollution. Traffic congestion remains one of the most persistent and complex challenges facing Egypt today, directly affecting road safety, fuel consumption, and citizens' life quality. Traditional traffic-light systems are programmed on certain timing cycles without an ability to adapt to sudden changes on roads, leading to wasted fuel and increased air pollution.

To deal with the extensive challenge of congestion, researchers and engineers have created several Intelligent Transport System (ITS) solutions. Adaptive Traffic Light Control Systems dynamically adjust signal timings based on real-time sensor data. Their main strength lies in reducing unnecessary idling and improving traffic flow, yet they often struggle in environments with unpredictable driver behavior. Dynamic Variable Message Signs (VMS) inform drivers about congestion, accidents, or safer alternative routes. Although useful during emergencies, VMS depends entirely on driver compliance and require expensive hardware and stable

communication networks. While each solution contributes to valuable insights, none fully address the problem of real-time congestion in busy urban intersections with limited budgets.

Based on the strengths and limitations of existing systems, the solution was designed focused on vision-based congestion detection and dynamic traffic-light control. The primary design requirements include 85% accuracy for the system to detect traffic density, adjusting green and red lights durations automatically based on congestion level, communicating updates to the public instantly, offering an affordable prototype suitable for deployment in Egyptian cities and integrating an emergency-vehicle priority feature.

When congestion exceeds five cars, the system extends green time for specific lanes while shortening red phases, ensuring smoother traffic flow. Additionally, a Telegram alert system informs drivers of real-time congestion and alternative routes. The solution offers high accuracy, remains cost-effective and easily scalable within existing infrastructure.

Results:

To determine the baseline, the traffic flow was detected using the old traffic system without using either the AI system or communication. The test was done for 70 seconds using toy cars to simulate real cars. Each one of the green and red lights intervals of

traffic light was 10s. The initial cars number was 8 and after 70s the cars numbers became 5 with 37.5% decreasing. The number of cars after every 10s is shown in table (1).

Table (1) Number of cars before using the system.

Time (S)	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70
No. of cars	8	5	8	6	7	6	8	5

A medium-size car in traffic congestion can produce 150-250g of CO₂ per minute (average 200/m) and 10-30g of CO per minute (average 20/m). (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency [EPA], 2008) By multiplying the pollution of one car with our results, the pollution may be produced from this prototype before applying my solution is shown in table (2).

Table (2) Pollution before using the system.

Time	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70
CO ₂	1600g	1000g	1600g	1200g	1400g	1200g	1600g	1000g
CO	160g	100g	160g	120g	140g	120g	160g	100g

After that, the AI Car-detector system, Smart-Controlled traffic lights, sending suggestions of alternative roads, and communication between emergency vehicles and drivers were used. The test was done for 70sec using toy cars. Congestion occurs when there are 5 cars on the road at the same time. In

condition of there is no congestion, each one of the green and red lights intervals of traffic light was 10s. If there is congestion, the green-light interval will automatically become 13s and the red-light interval will become 7s. The initial cars number was 8 and after 70s the cars numbers became 2 with 75% decreasing. The number of cars after every interval is shown in table (3).

Table (3) Number of cars after using the system.

Time (S)	0	10	13	20	30	40	50	53	60	70
No. of cars	8	5	3	7	4	8	5	3	6	2

The pollution may be produced from the prototype after applying my solution is shown in table (4).

Table (4) Pollution after using the system.

Time	0	10	13	20	30	40	50	53	60	70
CO ₂	1600	1000	600	1400	800	1600	1000	600	1200	400
CO	160	100	60	140	80	160	100	60	120	40

By comparing the results before and after applying the system, we find that after 70 seconds the number of cars decreased from 5 cars to 2 cars. The amount of CO₂ and CO decreased from 1000g and 100g to 400g and 40g respectively. In addition, the waiting time through the 70s decreased from 30s to 24s (20% reduction).

Discussion:

There was higher traffic congestion before using this system because the traffic light intervals were equal even though there was congestion in one road, however there wasn't congestion in the interrupting road. In addition, other drivers who aren't on that road weren't informed by road conditions. Therefore, in a small prototype, congestion decreased by only 37.5% in 70sec.

To make the test after applying the system, the test of the project is divided into some stages and conditions:

First, when there was no congestion, the traffic lights function like regular traffic lights, green light turned on for 10s, and red light turned on for 10s alternatively.

Second, when there was congestion (number of cars are more than 5 cars at the same moment),

1. The duration of the green and red lights was automatically adjusted, which the green light turned on for 13s and red light for 7s alternatively.
2. People received messages via Telegram bot that there is congestion on this road and got suggestions for alternative roads.
3. When there was an emergency vehicle such as an ambulance, that vehicle sent a message to the system, and then the public received notifications to clear the emergency lane.
4. The number of cars is displayed to the public via a website to monitor the traffic situation.

Initially, the ESP32-CAM system was used for car detection; it was cheap and of average quality, but it was very slow and suffered delays. So, it's replaced with a USB Webcam; it's cheaper and works faster than ESP32-CAM.

After using the USB Webcam, the prototype worked with high efficiency and congestion decreased by 75% in 70sec.

Future work should include more accurate measurements, which can be achieved in challenging conditions by integrating both high-resolution cameras and thermal or infrared sensors. Furthermore, creating a mobile application that represents a dashboard with real-time traffic alert information for drivers could even stretch the societal influence of the system by helping users to drive to less congested roads and thus better manage traffic in general.

Materials and Methods:

At the beginning of the analysis process, a USB camera was used to capture videos of cars and stream it to be analyzed. After that, YOLOv8 was used to detect cars, motorbikes, and people. Then, DeepSORT tracks objects over time and gives them an ID for tracking once.

Second, in normal condition, the green-light of the traffic light module turns on for 10 seconds, then it turns off and the red-light turns on for another 10 seconds. In the congestion condition, the traffic light receives an order from an Arduino UNO to make the green-light turns on for 13 sec, and the red-light turns on for 7 sec alternatively.

Third, in the congestion condition, the drivers receive an alert message on their Telegram using the “Traffic_Congestion” Telegram bot. This message contains the name of the road that the congestion is in, suggestion of alternative roads and their locations.

Fourth, when there is an emergency vehicle such as ambulance on the road, the driver sends an “Emergency” message to the bot, then other drivers receive a message to clear the emergency lane.

Fifth, the back-end server receives the number of cars and the traffic situation to display to the public on the front-end.

System operation was managed by Python and an Arduino Uno microcontroller.

The complete control script is publicly available on GitHub:

https://github.com/Mostafa-saleh-01/Traffic_Enhancer.git

In this solution, the waiting time through 70 sec decreased from 30s to 24s by 20% efficiency. The efficiency was calculated as:

$$Efficiency = \left(\frac{W_i - W_f}{W_i} \right) \times 100$$

Where W_i and W_f are initial and final waiting time respectively.

The communication between the system and the drivers is based on wireless communication and wired communication via optical fibers, which the message transmits through them, which are characterized by high speed, low noise, and transport over long distances.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the developed AI-based vehicle detection and smart traffic-light system successfully proved its ability to manage congestion and improve traffic flow. With accuracy of approximately 90%, the system consistently detects and tracks vehicles in real-time. The system provided more efficiency than the traditional fixed-timing methods by adjusting the green and red light durations during congestion.

The integration of the materials we have used allowed the system to operate reliably. The automatic congestion alerts are sent through Telegram, further enabling users to make valid decisions and consider alternative routes when road density increases.

Overall, the project has successfully met its objectives in addressing traffic congestion challenges in Egypt. While the system performed effectively within controlled testing conditions, we can confidently say that the work we have done provides a strong foundation for implementing more advanced intelligent transportation systems (ITS) and contributes to the wide vision of developing smart-city technologies across Egypt.

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Figures and Captions:

